

Reindeer husbandry is more than herding – Contemporary roles of women in reindeer husbandry in Finland

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ABSTRACT

Women's role in reindeer husbandry has received little attention and women have been largely excluded from the public image and management of the livelihood in Finland. We adopted a mixed-methods approach to examine the role of women in reindeer husbandry, focusing on the practices and agency of female herders from the 1980s to the present. Although women have historically been underrepresented in official roles and decision-making related to reindeer husbandry, this is changing. Changes in society and attitudes, herding traditions as well as increased gender equality and a higher educational level and technological development, among others, have affected the practices and agency of women in reindeer husbandry. In addition, challenges related to rapid land-use expansion and intensification as well as climate change require extra work from both men and women. Our study suggests that increased diversification in reindeer husbandry has created new opportunities and roles for women. In addition to physical work, such as gathering herds and round-ups, the contemporary tasks of women include office work, work in supplementary livelihoods and housekeeping round the year. In the 2020s, the proportion of women in reindeer husbandry, both as practitioners and in management roles, is still low. However, along with the changing role of women, the share of female reindeer owners and the number of reindeer they own is gradually increasing, as is the share of female trustees and herding district employees. A new trend of young and educated women entering the livelihood and having more active and diverse roles than earlier is clearly emerging.

1. Introduction

Rural communities with substantial natural resources dependency around the world, such as farming and pastoralist cultures, show a highly gendered division of labour, and reindeer herding communities appear not to be an exception (Amft, 2000; Reed, 2003; Buchanan et al., 2016). While the role of women in reindeer husbandry has been scarcely addressed in research, a wealth of literature exists on the conditions of rural women and gender issues in farming in northern Fennoscandia (Brandth, 2002; Sireni, 2002, 2015; Silvasti, 2003; Kallioniemi and Kymäläinen, 2012). We will first turn to these studies to provide a general backdrop against which to address the specificities of contemporary women's roles in reindeer husbandry. Research has identified various discourses that reflect the role of women in European agriculture (Brandth, 2002). One such discourse, the "family farm" narrative,

portrays women as dependent on their husbands, compromising their own rights and needs. In this narrative, their roles are described as marginal or invisible. The discourse of "masculinization" is male-dominated. One reason for this is the increased mechanization of agriculture (Sireni, 2002). The third and more recent discourse, "detraditionalization and diversity", reflects a situation in which women do not accept the roles considered as traditional on farms. In Finnish rural studies, the roles of women and gender relations have received relatively little attention (see, however, Siiskonen, 1983, 1990; Högbäck and Siiskonen, 1996; Sireni, 2002, 2015; Silvasti, 2003; Kallioniemi and Kymäläinen, 2012). Earlier research often portrayed rural women as prisoners of patriarchal structures and external forces affecting agriculture, with little power of influence (Sireni, 2002). Our study examines contemporary roles of women in reindeer husbandry in Finland. Our work cannot be directly linked to earlier rural studies because reindeer husbandry differs significantly from farming. For

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Abbreviations

HD	herding district
RHA	reindeer husbandry area
ATV	all-terrain vehicle
GPS	geographic positioning system
WWII	Second World War (1939–1945)

example, reindeer herding traditions and cultures differ; reindeer are semi-domesticated instead of domesticated; grazing rights are independent of land ownership, and there is seasonal pasture rotation (Helle and Jaakkola, 2008).

Most studies on women in reindeer husbandry have been conducted in Norway and Sweden (Eikjok, 1988, 2007; Amft, 2000; Joks, 2001, 2007; Kuokkanen, 2009, 2020; Uden, 2010; Buchanan et al., 2016; Lidestav et al., 2020; Asztalos Morell, 2021), as well as in northwestern Russia (Tuisku, 1999, 2001; Ruotsala, 2002; Bogdanova et al., 2021; Istomin, 2022). These studies have primarily emphasized Indigenous aspects, with many focusing on Sámi women and the impacts of colonial history in Sápmi. Sámi feminist activists have argued that when reindeer husbandry is viewed solely as a means of producing meat, as has been the trend since the 1950s, the contributions of women are often rendered invisible (e.g., Eikjok, 1988, 2007; Joks, 2001; Buchanan et al., 2016). In Finland, where both Sámi and non-Sámi people practice reindeer husbandry, few studies have been conducted on the role of women in this livelihood (Jääskö, 1998; Ruotsala, 2007, 2009; Joon and Kesitalo, 2021; Kylli, 2021). However, historical accounts of women's work exist, including those by Paulaharju (1927), Itkonen (1948), Lehtola (2012), and Kylli (2021). These studies demonstrate that the role of women in reindeer husbandry has varied greatly by time and location. However, a gendered labor division, in which women and men have different yet complementary roles, is evident in all herding traditions.

The development of reindeer herding traditions has greatly impacted the gendered division of labor within the livelihood in Finland. The western tradition of reindeer herding evolved from contact with the nomadic Sámi tradition, which spread from central Scandinavia during the 16th and 17th centuries (Heikkinen, 2006). In nomadic Sámi herding, extensive pasture use meant that Fell Sámi families roamed long distances with their herds. This most likely increased women's participation in herding, thus reducing the gendered division of labor (Fur, 2006). Paulaharju (1927) mentions women herders who could navigate the fells alone, handle suopunki (lasso used to catch animals), and drive reindeer sleds. In the eastern herding tradition, which originated with the Forest, Inari, and Skolt Sámi, as well as Finnish peasants, herding was on a smaller scale. It was stationary and combined with other livelihoods. A gendered division of labor was typical in this tradition (see more detailed information in Paulaharju, 1927; Itkonen, 1948; Kortessalmi, 2007; Heikkinen, 2006).

The closing of borders to migration between nation-states in the late 19th century and the establishment of the herding co-operative system in Finland led to more stationary reindeer husbandry in the whole reindeer husbandry area (RHA) (Heikkinen, 2006; Stark et al., 2023). By the beginning of the 20th century, most herding families had moved into permanent settlements, and dairy farming had also been adopted in large parts of the RHA. These developments likely contributed to reindeer herding becoming a primarily male-dominated activity (Jouste, 2011). Regardless of the herding tradition, tending to cattle along with performing housework and taking care of children seems to be most commonly a women's job, which has largely tied women to the house (Itkonen, 1948; Kylli, 2021). While noting that there has not been a task women had not done, women would mainly participate in seasonal herding work such as calf markings and round-ups, making fodder, and

the work at home, such as feeding the reindeer and household work (Jääskö, 1998).

Reindeer husbandry has experienced fundamental changes since the mid-20th century, including a shift from a subsistence economy to a financial economy, a stronger focus on meat production, as well as the introduction of snowmobiles, all-terrain vehicles (ATVs) and other new technology, such as mobile phones and Global Positioning System (GPS) collars for reindeer (Helle and Jaakkola, 2008). In most herding districts (HDs), winter feeding has become a regular part of herding in the 1980s and 1990s (Kortessalmi, 2007; Turunen and Vuojala-Magga, 2014). These changes have also affected the role of women. The effort towards a more profitable livelihood has led to rationalization and mechanization of reindeer husbandry, which has in some studies been interpreted as strengthening masculinization of the livelihood and marginalization of women from core practices of herding (Amft, 2000; Buchanan et al., 2016). At the same time, the combined effects of extreme weather events, multiple land uses and growing predator populations have increased the workload for all, also female herders, and challenged their skills (e.g., Turunen et al., 2016, 2024; Rasmus et al., 2020, 2022).

Contemporary roles of women in reindeer husbandry in Finland are not well known. Our study is situated in rural geography and examines the everyday practices and experiences of women in reindeer herding communities. One of the central analytical categories here is 'gender', which we define as the social structure built around biological sex (Gregson et al., 1997), as well as something that people perform, or 'do', (Risman, 2009), and as the socially produced content of femininity or masculinity (Sireni, 2002). Gender roles are shaped by expectations and assumptions about gender in social interactions, as well as by gendered opportunities and constraints at the institutional and organizational levels, such as in the distribution of resources and status (Risman and Davis, 2013). In our case, these translate into expectations and assumptions about gender in reindeer-herding communities. Gendered opportunities and constraints can be seen, for example, in the ownership of reindeer and the gender division among HD officials.

An interesting question here is the gendered use of space. Massey (1984, 1994) argues that the concept of place is defined through social relations, and that social relations in space also vary due to gender roles and relations, for example. The gendered patterns of spatial activity have been studied by McDowell (1993a, 1993b) and Sireni (2002) within the framework of feminist geography. When studying livelihoods such as reindeer husbandry, how space is used is a particularly relevant question. Reindeer husbandry is a mobile livelihood involving tasks that need to be carried out in pastures, forests, fells and at home. This economic activity is also part of culture and tradition. Discussions about who is a herder, what herders do and where they work can reveal interesting aspects of social structures and how spaces for production and care are understood and utilized (Buchanan et al., 2016).

Gender relations often refer to the structures and practices that produce and maintain material and power inequalities between women and men. These inequalities can manifest as a subordinate position for women (Gregson et al., 1997). We acknowledge these earlier approaches and findings, but seek a way forward by building our conceptual viewpoint on theories of practice and agency. In the practice theory by Bourdieu (1977), practices are conceptualized as "what people do", or an individual's performance carried out in everyday life. Practices and perceptions on these (including patterns of spatial activity) are guided by social conventions, rules and values, but can be impacted and changed for example when confronting a new way of doing.

'Agency' is a central concept in practice theory; it refers to willingness and capacity to act based on one's identity and cultural patterns (Eteläpelto et al., 2013). Elements of agency include voluntariness, structures and resources enabling choices, and the power to choose one's own course of action (Manlosa, 2022). Expectations and assumptions related to gender ("who should do what") can impact women's agency in any profession. Hobson (2011) discusses agency through capability theory, distinguishing between functioning and capabilities.

This involves considering not only what people do, but also their capability of doing. Willingness does not necessarily lead to action, and while freedom of agency is always constrained by societal structures, exercising agency is a matter of degree in the sense that some face more constraints and inequalities than do others. The individual's set of capabilities can be assessed, as well as how these capabilities are promoted by institutions and policies in certain settings (Hobson, 2011; Hobson et al., 2013).

The main aim of our study is to better understand the contemporary roles of women in reindeer husbandry in Finland by examining them through the lenses of practice, agency (with an emphasis on the capabilities and constraints) and gendered use of space. We seek to give voice to the women in reindeer husbandry by taking their own perceptions and experiences as objects of our study. Our research questions are:

- What are the practices of women in contemporary reindeer husbandry, and how are the elements of agency experienced by women?
- How has the role of women in reindeer husbandry changed over the past few decades? How has their status changed as a reindeer owner, and as an HD official?
- How does women's work vary in different regions of the RHA?
- What are the various drivers that have influenced the role of women in reindeer husbandry; what promotes or constrains their agency?
- What are women's hopes for the future regarding their role in reindeer husbandry?

We answer these questions based on literature, statistics and other archival materials, and discussions from three participatory workshops held for women of reindeer-herding families in northern Finland during 2021–2022. The goal of our work is to increase the visibility of women's work and role in reindeer husbandry and to support networking and capacity building within reindeer husbandry communities.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Archival and statistical data

We used statistical records maintained by the Reindeer Herders' Association to study the role of women as reindeer owners during 1991/1992–2021/2022¹ within the reindeer husbandry area (RHA) (Fig. 1a). The Reindeer Herders' Association is the central organisation that represents reindeer herders in Finland. It protects the interests of reindeer herding communities (HDs) and promotes cooperation between them. The Association addresses common issues related to reindeer herding, including matters concerning legislation, land use, and predator policy. The Association also provides statements and advice to the authorities and herders, organizes training and research, and maintains statistics and registers on reindeer herding (Reindeer Herders' Association, 2024).

To be a reindeer owner, one must possess both an earmark² and reindeer as well as belong to a HD where to manage them (Reindeer Husbandry Act 848/1990). Typically the children of reindeer herding families get their own earmarks and some reindeer already at an early age. There is a difference between being a reindeer *owner* and being a reindeer *herder*, the latter being someone who actively participates in herding work. In Finnish the word for a professional reindeer herder is

poromies ('reindeer man'). There are ca. 4,300 reindeer owners in Finland, with ca. 1,000 full-time herders, and ca. 1,000 persons to whom it is a secondary occupation. Most (90 %) reindeer owners have less than 100 reindeer, with many participating in herding work only occasionally. The majority of the herders have additional income sources where reindeer herding is part of a mixed economy. Hence, a woman owning reindeer is a sign of her being part of the reindeer herding culture, but that information alone does not tell us much about the nature of her participation in reindeer husbandry.

The RHA is divided into 54 herding districts (HD); and reindeer have to be herded within the area of the HD to which they belong. These units are also referred to as herding cooperatives, particularly when the community formed by herders is emphasized. In this article, we use the expression "herding district (HD)" throughout for clarity. In the Sámi tradition, *siidas* are herding groups often based on kinship and are of greater practical importance in everyday herding than the HD. Also, the more southern HDs may be divided into units, such as *tokkakunta* or *roikka*, that are based on e.g. kinship or place of residence.

Each HD is led by a Chief of District (manager) chosen by the general meeting of the HD. *Chief of District* is called *poroisäntä* in Finnish, which is a gender-specific title implying that the person is male. In addition, the general meeting chooses a Vice-chief of District and a four-member board. The board directs and oversees the HD's activities, and its term lasts three years (Reindeer Husbandry Act 1990/848). The board nominates staff members to perform in various roles, including treasurer, secretary, countman, foreman, slaughterhouse supervisor, damage appraiser and others (e.g. inspector, contact person of occupational health). The Chief of District leads and coordinates the tasks of the HD and the decisions made by the board as well as represents the HD. The main task of the countman is to keep record of the reindeer numbers in the roundups (Reindeer Husbandry Act 1990/848). The role of a countman is a position of trust, and an essential part of the HD's staff. The treasurer is in charge of the HD's finances – another position of trust and responsibility, which does not require herding skills. Treasurers act as secretaries during the boards' meetings and may write statements on behalf of the HD and prepare the HD's meetings with the Chief of District. The treasurer has an overview of the HD's activities and situation. The appraiser assesses damage caused by reindeer to agricultural land, or damage caused by traffic to reindeer, among others.

From 1948 onwards, HDs have been obliged to compile an annual management report to the Reindeer Herders Association,³ and the reporting has covered the whole RHA. Before that, the records were fragmentary e.g. due to the turmoil of WWII. The reports exhibit different writing styles, and data may be missing due to inexact or incomplete records in some HDs for some years. The reports are available at the archives of the Provincial Museum in Oulu (-1981/1982) and the Reindeer Herders' Association in Rovaniemi (1982/1983 -). Several name changes, mergers and divisions of the HDs have taken place during the study period. Therefore, we were not able to analyze the development of the gender division within the individual HDs.

We used the annual management reports of the HDs to study the roles of women at the institutional and organizational level of the livelihood; the gender division of HD officials (Text A1). We calculated the proportion of women and men within the boards and the staff of HDs annually for the period from 1949/1950 to 1981/1982. Most of the reports include the names of the Chief of District, the Vice-chief of District and the treasurer. From 1976/1977 onwards, the names of board members start to appear. For the period 1982–2021, only every fifth report was investigated. From 1984 onwards, the documentation can be considered reliable, because all names of the board members and other staff are listed and the minutes are typed. In our view, it is possible to trace quite reliably the development of the gender division in two

¹ Comparable information from earlier years was not available. Since reindeer herding year starts 1 June and ends 31 May, we use xxxx/xxxx form in the text and tables – a practice which has been used since the oldest available annual management reports of HDs.

² Earmark on a reindeer signifies ownership. One can possess several earmarks through inheritance or through buying someone's herd. In Sámi reindeer herding, earmarks (and reindeer) typically change owners within families and selling to outsiders is more rare.

³ Reindeer Herders' Association was established in 1948; it replaced the previous Poronjalostusyhdistys also as a record keeper.

Fig. 1. Reindeer husbandry area (RHA), including the workshop locations of Inari, Rovaniemi and Kuusamo marked with red dots and the participants' herding districts (HDs) with their official numbers, marked in darker blue. The participants came to the Inari workshop from Muddusjärvi (4), Hammastunturi (8), Sallivaara (9), Muotkatunturi (10), Käsivarsi (12), Sattasniemi (17) and Lappi (21); to the Rovaniemi workshop from Alakylä (16), Salla (24), Pyhä-Kallio (26), Poikajärvi (28), Orajärvi (31) and Oivanki (46); and to the Kuusamo workshop from Posion Livo (38), Isosydänmaa (39), Alakitka (42), Kallioluoma (45) and Oivanki (46). Map ©Arto Vitikka. Arctic Centre, University of Lapland. Data: ©Runfola et al., (2020), ©Arctic Indigenous languages and revitalization: an online educational resource, 2023 (a). Female reindeer herders participating in the Inari workshop. Photo: Minna Turunen (b). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

statuses over seven decades: the Chief of District and the treasurer. The reports for the period from 1981/1982 to 2020/2021 enable a more thorough analysis of the official roles held by women within the HDs, including tracing how the roles have changed through four decades and identifying geographical differences in them (Text A1).

2.2. Workshops

Three workshops were organized for female members of reindeer-herding communities in northern Finland (Fig. 1ab). The first workshop was held on 15 September 2021 on the Konttaniemi Reindeer Farm

in Rovaniemi (central RHA); the second workshop took place on 3 May 2022 in Hotel Inari in Inari (the Sámi homeland); and the third workshop was organized on 12 September 2022 in Hotel Tropiikki in Kuusamo (south-eastern RHA). Each workshop had 11–14 (37 in total) participants.

Participants were selected through purposive sampling based mostly on the authors' contacts from previous projects. The selection was based on women's potential interest, willingness, and availability to participate as well as their location within a reasonable distance (max 200 km) from the workshop location. In addition, we informed the HD managers about the workshops and they distributed the invitations to the women herders of their HD. Information about the workshop spread also through snowballing. Participants came from 19 HDs (Fig. 1a). In addition, there were 3–6 female researchers facilitating each workshop. Since none of the organizers was fluent in Sámi languages, the workshops were held in Finnish. All participants were fluent in Finnish and they were also free to converse in Sámi during the discussions. The workshops lasted 3–4 h, they included a complimentary dinner for all participants and plenty of time for informal socializing. Participants' travel expenses were reimbursed by the organizers. We describe our research as action research. The main focus of the workshops was on studying the roles of women in reindeer husbandry. With the workshops, we sought to establish a foundation that encourages participants to raise their awareness and continuously learn from each other (Clark et al., 2000).

The group of women participating in the workshops was diverse. The mean age of participants was 39 years; the youngest was born in 2001 (20 years old) and the oldest in 1967 (55 years old). Despite our efforts to reach potential participants, for example through the use of multiple communication channels, no older women (over 55 years old) participated in the workshops. Two women had babies with them; and mother and daughter, both active in herding, participated together. Some participants had been introduced to the lifestyle through marriage. The ethnicity of herders was not asked, but we assume that all participants in Rovaniemi and most in Kuusamo were from the Finnish herding tradition. In Inari, we assume that more than half of the participants were from the Sámi herding tradition. Reindeer herding was a full-time occupation for a few participants, but for most it was a subsidiary occupation. Many had a job outside herding, but they would support and participate in the livelihood when needed. About two thirds of the participants had their own business ID, mainly in reindeer herding but also in tourism, handicrafts, sales, forestry and healthcare. Most participants were highly educated; outside reindeer husbandry they had jobs in management, research and development, teaching as well as veterinary medicine, for example.

In each of the three workshops, participants were assigned a number from 1 to 3 and they formed small groups based on these numbers. In terms of the workshops, we conducted an applied qualitative research study. We created specific, predetermined questions to guide the process, from data collection to analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Creswell and Creswell, 2018). The task of the small groups was to answer three main questions asked by the workshop leaders and to present their responses on a large sheet of paper: 1. What are your seasonal tasks (practices) in reindeer husbandry, at present? 2. What tasks related to reindeer husbandry were performed by your mother and grandmother? How did the women's tasks in the past differ from those at present, and why? 3. How do you see the role of women in reindeer-herding families in the future? The third question allowed participants to put forward their future scenarios related to their role and agency in reindeer husbandry. We define the "recent past" as the period from approximately 1970 to 2000. This was a time of rapid changes in land use, climate and herding practices. We define the "present" as the period from approximately 2000 to 2025. By "future" we mean the coming decades up to 2050. Following the work in small groups, the results were shared and

discussed by all. No analysis was conducted to examine intersectional variations across age, marital/family status and occupation. Open discussion included themes related to expectations and assumptions about female herders, and to their agency and factors promoting or limiting it.

The discussions were purposefully not recorded to create an un-stressed and relaxed atmosphere, but detailed notes were taken by the researchers. The main steps in our qualitative data analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Creswell and Creswell, 2018) were to systematically study the graphs of women's seasonal work produced by the participants and to analyze the notes from the joint discussions that the researchers took. The data were organized by question and response, with these combinations forming the basis of the Results section. In addition, 'Drivers affecting women's roles' and 'The agency of female herders in male-dominated livelihoods' are presented as separate chapters in the results because they sparked exceptionally lively debate among the participants. Fig. 9 is based on discussions held during the workshop. While some of the concepts depicted in the image were employed by the participants, the authors also conceptualized issues that arose during the discussions. In this way, the figure is the result of a saturation process. At the end of each workshop, participants were asked to provide feedback. Additionally, the researchers engaged in reflective discussions after each workshop. The results of the workshops have already been returned to the herding communities in the form of an article "Women's role in reindeer husbandry stays and becomes more diverse" published in *Poromies* ('Reindeer Herder'), a professional journal of reindeer herders (Rasmus et al., 2022a,b).

3. Results

3.1. Women as reindeer owners from 1990/1991 to 2021/2022

The total number of reindeer owners has decreased during 1990/1991–2021/2022 from 7,556 to 4,313 (Reindeer Herders' Association, 2024) (Fig. 2). The share of retired people (over 65-year-olds) has decreased the most, and at the same time the proportion of reindeer owners who are under 17 years of age has increased and has remained thereafter rather stable (Fig. 3ab, Table A1). The reindeer owners are thus getting younger on average (Table A2)

Fig. 2. Gender division of reindeer owners within the RHA. The percentages above the columns indicate the share of female reindeer owners of all reindeer owners within the RHA during the period 1990/1991–2021/2022.

Fig. 3a. Number of male reindeer owners in different age classes during reindeer herding years 1990/1991–2021/2022 within the RHA (Reindeer Herders’ Association 2024)

Fig. 3b. Number of female reindeer owners in different age classes during reindeer herding years 1990/1991–2021/2022 within the RHA (Reindeer Herders’ Association, 2024).

Fig. 4. The number of reindeer owned by females and males; as well as percentages next to the columns indicating the share of reindeer owned by females of all reindeer within the RHA during the period 1990/1991–2021/2022. The total number of reindeer does not include the reindeer owned by HDs or estates.

The number of female reindeer owners has remained roughly the same (Fig. 2, Table A1). This means that the share of women in the overall number of reindeer owners is gradually increasing. In 2020/2021 as many as 32 % of reindeer owners were women. The gradual increase is caused by the corresponding decrease in the share of male reindeer owners (Fig. 2, Table A1), leading to an increasing female presence. During 1995/1996 there were no women under 17 years of age owning reindeer, but in 2005/2006 there is almost the same number of young women and men (Rehtonen, 2019).

The total number of reindeer within the RHA has decreased during 1990/1991–2021/2022 from 249,644 to 185,274 (Reindeer Herders' Association, 2024), but the number of reindeer owned by women has remained roughly the same (Fig. 4). For this reason, the share of reindeer owned by women is gradually increasing. In 2020/2021, as many as 18 % of the reindeer were owned by women.

3.2. The official roles of women in reindeer husbandry from 1949/1950 to 2020/2021

Women have been seldom represented in the management of reindeer husbandry at the local, regional or national level. At the local level, there have been a few women serving as Chiefs of District Vice-Chiefs of District or as members of the HDs' boards, as well as in the staff appointed by the boards (Fig. 5ab). The share of women within the HDs' board members has varied between 0 % and 5 % during the period 1984/1985–2021/2022 within the RHA. The first record of a female board member we found was in the annual management report (1983/1984) of Näätämä, the Sámi homeland. The first woman ever to be appointed first as a Vice-Chief of District (2001/2002), and then as a Chief of District (2003/2004–2008/2009) was in Kaldoaivi, the Sámi homeland. During the period 2007–2012, the number of females in the HD boards increased gradually and has remained rather stable since then (Fig. 5b). Appointment of women to the HD board is a bit more common in the Sámi homeland than elsewhere in the RHA. For example, in 2021/2022, a total of 61 % of all female board members, and 55 % of all females appointed HD staff, were from the Sámi homeland. In the

southern parts of the RHA, where reindeer husbandry is more often a subsidiary occupation and the majority of herders are of Finnish ethnicity, several HDs (Vanttaus, Timisjärvi, Tolva, Taivalkoski, Pintamo, Kiiminki and Kollaja) had no record of having had women during the period 1984/1985–2021/2022 either in the board or as staff (Fig. 6).

The proportion of women appointed as staff of the HDs has varied between 4 % and 11 % during the period 1984/1985–2021/2022. Women have worked in the following roles: countman, treasurer, foreman, appraiser, weight man, bookkeeper and cleaner, among others. The role of the countman is the most common job of women in the HD. In Lappi and Muddusjärvi, in the Sámi homeland, almost all countmen listed in the annual management reports are women. The first record we found of a woman appointed as a treasurer was in Alakylä (1954/1955), the central part of the RHA. Since the 1980s, the proportion of women in this particular job has increased rapidly (Fig. 5b). Women have also been appointed as appraisers. In 2012, a female was appointed as the first-ever contact person for occupational well-being in Kemi-Sompio HD, the northern part of the RHA.

The proportion of women appointed to the board of the Reindeer Herders' Association (regional level) has been small as well: the first female member was appointed in 2000, and one or two women were appointed for each three-year term until 2024. For the period 2024–2026, no women were selected for the board. The Reindeer Herders' Association has had a female executive director since 2010 (Reindeer Herders' Association, 2024). All four advisers of the association are females. The positions related to the governance of reindeer husbandry in the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (national level) have lacked women (Reindeer Herders' Association, 2024).

3.3. Past practices of women in reindeer husbandry

According to workshop participants, a clear division of labor existed between men and women in reindeer husbandry before the 1950s. This division was rather inevitable, particularly in the Rovaniemi and Kuusamo regions, where cattle were commonly kept and where at least one adult would always be tied to the home. Women took care of the children and all the household work since men's work often involved staying long periods far away from home. Women were in charge of making and maintaining clothes and taking care of cooking, children, cattle as well as "home reindeer". Men took care of the herds. There were clear gendered patterns in the spatial activity. Gathering and moving reindeer to round-ups by foot or ski was time-consuming, and herders spent weeks away from their homes.

The participants from the Rovaniemi and Kuusamo regions shared memories about women's participation in making fodder and feeding reindeer in the winter from the end of the 1970s onwards. From the 1970s and 1980s onwards, women were also often responsible for transporting family members to calf markings in summer and to round-ups in autumn. In round-ups, women could act as countmen, and they also participated in meat processing. Women made beds and prepared food for the herders during these events. Before ATVs were adopted in the 1980s and 1990s, gathering reindeer in autumn was done by foot, and even after that, those who did not have their own ATVs continued to do the work by foot.

The participants in the Kuusamo and Rovaniemi workshops reported that in the central part of the RHA, keeping cattle was women's job, which is why women participated less in reindeer herding work further away from home. According to the participants of the Inari workshop, the division of herding tasks was more equal between men and women in the northernmost HDs because cattle were not commonly kept there.

Fig. 5. The number of women appointed to the HD boards and staff during the period 1984/1985–2021/2022 (a) and the number of women appointed as a treasurer of a HD within the RHA during the period 1954/1955–2021/2022 (b).

Keeping cattle in reindeer herding families is rare nowadays. Additionally, participants view the decline in the number of skilled herders performing physical labor in forests and fells as problematic. However, this development has also made it possible for women to enter the field of reindeer herding. "There are fewer folks, so even women have been taken along" (Kuusamo). Participants agreed that, from the 1970s to the 2000s, women often held jobs outside herding to support their families, but nowadays, a much larger proportion of women in herding families have paid jobs.

3.4. Contemporary practices of women in reindeer husbandry

Regarding the changing roles of women in reindeer husbandry, the workshop participants referred to the common saying that "behind every successful man there stands a woman", and had the perception that in every reindeer herder household there has been a woman ("akka") who has "kept things going". What has changed is that women are now coming to the forefront with their agency. The discussions clearly revealed that women have a holistic understanding of reindeer husbandry, not only as a specific line of work but also as a way of life which includes the whole

Fig. 6. HDs divided into classes based on the time when the first woman was appointed as a member of either a HD board or staff.

family and where the line between work and private life is blurry.

The workshop discussions revealed the diverse seasonal tasks of women in reindeer husbandry and provided insight into spatial activity

Fig. 8. Nowadays, women play a significant role in calf marking. During this process, the calves are given earmarks to indicate ownership. Women often catch and hold the calves while they are earmarked. Earmarking requires skill and knowledge of the different types of marks. Women also carry the calves to the calf marking site, which is physically demanding. Some women, like Iida Melamies, a reindeer herder and one of the co-authors, may also perform the earmarking themselves. Photo: Viola Ukkola.

patterns in women’s work (Fig. 7, Table A3). Although female herders participate in tasks such as marking calves (Fig. 8), gathering reindeer, and slaughter, it became evident that they most often perform reindeer husbandry tasks at home or in the yard. Male herders, particularly those in the northernmost HDs, still primarily perform herding tasks located farthest from home. Some participants in the Inari workshop said that, due to long distances and bad weather, they have had to stay home with their children. Some tasks, such as office work and handicrafts, are not location-specific.

Fig. 7. A seasonal cycle of women’s contemporary tasks in reindeer husbandry, based on the reports from the women herders’ workshops held in Inari, Kuusamo and Rovaniemi during the period 2021–2022. The inner circle includes tasks conducted all year round; these are mostly conducted at home or in the yard, whereas the tasks marked in the outer circle are mostly conducted in the yard or pasture areas. Some tasks (e.g., office work) are not tied to a specific location. For more detailed information on the women’s seasonal work, see Table A3.

Fig. 9. Examples of drivers of change promoting the agency of female reindeer herders in Finland. Here, 'role' encompasses the expectations and assumptions related to practices and the opportunities and constraints at the institutional and organizational levels, such as those relating to reindeer ownership and official roles in the management of livelihoods. The diagram and its concepts were developed in collaboration with workshop participants and researchers.

3.4.1. Multiple sources of income

As was often the case in the past, when mixed economies and reindeer herding were practiced alongside each other, it is still typical for reindeer herding families to have multiple sources of income. Here women often have a prominent role, since the hands-on herding work that requires spending long periods in the forest or on the fells belongs typically to men. Multiple sources of income mean increased resilience of the household in the face of potential crises touching reindeer husbandry. But this arrangement also brings the challenge of combining ad hoc schedules of reindeer herding and other work commitments.

Reindeer husbandry as a livelihood is becoming more diverse than earlier through links forged with meat processing, product development and other supporting operations, as well as supplementary livelihoods such as reindeer-based tourism, all of which have become an intrinsic part of reindeer husbandry. This has opened up new possibilities for women. The livelihood has been confronted with new needs and ways of doing things, which has changed practices. The workshop participants reported that in family businesses of reindeer-based tourism activities, taming, training and taking care of reindeer are central tasks of women.

Gathering and processing materials for handicrafts, and doing crafts both for the family's own use and for sale is mostly women's work. Women often market and sell the products in their family businesses – in addition to meat products, also tourism services and handicrafts. In the Inari workshop, women's traditional role in making handicrafts was emphasized more than in the workshops held in Kuusamo and Rovaniemi, which may be related to production of traditional Sámi handicrafts. Production of handicrafts included preparation of footwear made of reindeer leg leather (*nutukkaat*), mittens, wool socks, hats, and work clothes not only for the family, but also for sale.

3.4.2. "Invisible" practices of female herders

In addition to physically demanding core duties strictly related to herding, such as gathering herds and slaughter, the participants considered "all the invisible background work" of their family businesses and housekeeping as work in reindeer husbandry. The list of tasks included most importantly office work and taking care of the family members, as well as the dietary, clothing and gear maintenance of the whole family throughout the year (Fig. 7, Table A3). The women reported that housekeeping includes taking care of children and domestic animals, doing dishes and laundry, taking care of bills, taking care of the

family's social life, giving emotional support to others as well as overseeing the "big picture", among others (Fig. 7, Table A3). In the Inari workshop, the participants listed the following tasks belonging solely to women: working as the family's "general secretary", taking care of day-to-day logistics and "reminding" reindeer herding men about different issues and taking care of work related to holidays and festivities. Autumn round-ups are a busy time, and while men might focus on the reindeer, women may have numerous tasks including herding, paid work, childcare and household chores.

Increasing office work forms a major part of women's tasks: financial planning, bookkeeping, writing applications for substitutes and compensations, compiling reindeer statistics, ordering supplies, writing statements, appraisal of traffic, agricultural and predator damages, and doing related background work, only to mention some. Work of the HD requires a new type of competence compared to earlier days, such as knowledge of land use planning and legislation, and skills for using map services and other applications, drones and GPS collars.

3.4.3. Childcare practices

Workshop discussions revealed the importance of involving children in herding work. This involvement was seen as crucial for sparking children's interest in the livelihood, building their confidence in their herding identity, and fostering their commitment to the livelihood and the way of life. Mothers see that children learn herding practices and skills, such as "reading nature" as well as social skills and responsibility (see also Rehtonen, 2025). A few participants shared recollections about attending gatherings and round-ups as children and schoolkids, for several days in a row – something that is also nowadays considered as an important part of upbringing.

In practice, there is great variation in how children are nowadays involved in herding work. Welfare services for families with children and the elderly are important in Finland. The development of municipal daycare systems for children under school age (Sireni, 2015; Salonen and Koivisto, 2024) has made life easier for reindeer-herding families. These systems also empower women to choose to work outside the home, whether that be paid employment or other activities that take place outside the home, such as in a workplace, company, factory, school or office. Women typically work outside home during the week, and during weekends, may think that "feeding reindeer and working outside brings a welcome balance". Children often take part in these

activities. In families where both parents practice herding, children either accompany the parents, or are “taken to grandma” or to daycare. Some workshop participants found the help from their friends and relatives – the network of women – extremely important.

Reaching school age may limit the opportunities for children to be involved in herding work. Even though the round-ups are nowadays often smaller, shorter and more commonly take place on weekends, attending them can still require absence from school. Participants reported that some schools and individual teachers share the reindeer herding families’ view that attending herding events is educational. However, some schools require students to apply for permission to be absent well in advance, which may be difficult due to the dependence on favorable weather conditions for gathering the animals.

3.5. Drivers affecting women’s roles

The workshop discussions revealed that many factors have contributed to the changing role of women in reindeer husbandry (Fig. 9.). The livelihood has been confronted with new needs and ways of working, resulting in changes related to practices and perceptions – including what is considered socially appropriate for men and women. The factors that promote or limit the agency of female herders have changed.

Society is constantly changing, marked by shifts in social structures and expectations and assumptions related to gender. Both women and men have become more educated, which contributes to the change of herding cultures as a whole. In general, women are less dependent on men than in the past. They are also becoming more actively involved in herding, as well as at institutional and organisational levels of livelihoods. The roles of men have changed, too, which has further improved the status of women in reindeer husbandry. The changing expectations and assumptions about gender in society as a whole have had a balancing impact on the division of work: nowadays also fathers take care of the home and children, for example. Also, male herders have become more willing to pack their backpacks themselves – even though some wives still “serve their husband”.

Natural conditions and cultural traditions can either limit or promote women’s agency in reindeer husbandry. Women herders in the Inari workshop reported that more extreme weather conditions and topography, and longer distances in the northernmost HDs compared to their more southern counterparts may compromise the capabilities of women to participate in herding tasks. Women often take children with them to autumn round-ups, but bad weather conditions or long distances may force the mother to stay at home: “if you have to go first 150 km by car and after that 15 km by snowmobile, it won’t be easy” (Inari).

According to participants, the increased mechanization during the 1980s and 1990s lessened the physical burden of herding work, making many physically demanding tasks easier for both men and women, and promoting the agency of female herders. They valued the development of road network, modern vehicles and equipment: “Roads and cars have come, you don’t have to stay in the forest for weeks, you just get into your Hiace [to get there] and can take your children with you” (Rovaniemi). The same holds true for digitalization: navigation even to the most remote pastures is easier using the GPS collars on reindeer and monitoring the herds using tablets and laptops. However, there can still be dangerous situations in harsh winter conditions when the snowmobile can get stuck and there is no possibility to call for help.

Changes in reindeer herding practices, particularly increased winter feeding of reindeer, has made women’s role more significant than earlier. The need for supplementary feeding has increased due to other land use and poor winter foraging conditions. In the changing climate, difficult snow conditions prevent reindeer from digging for lichen (see Turunen and Vuojala-Magga, 2014). Women’s tasks related to feeding and producing feed were most often emphasized in the Rovaniemi and Kuusamo workshops, because winter feeding of reindeer, especially in home enclosures, and fodder production on agricultural land are most common in the southern RHA (Turunen and Vuojala-Magga, 2014).

These tasks included “feeding”, “taking care of fences and bringing reindeer into pens”, “preparing agricultural fields”, “producing and ordering winter feeds” (Table A3). The participants also agreed that women’s role is also economically important, because it is often the woman who pays the commercial feeds, because she is most often the one who has a regular job outside home.

Coping with other land uses and increased predator populations have greatly affected women’s tasks in reindeer husbandry. Discussion on both of these topics was emphasized more in the Rovaniemi and Kuusamo workshops than in the Inari workshop (Table A3). Land-use conflicts particularly in southeastern RHA occur between reindeer herders and farmers, permanent residents or second-home owners due to damage caused by reindeer to agricultural fields and gardens (Hiedanpää et al., 2020). Women’s tasks related to land use included “moving harmful reindeer away from agricultural fields” and “finding, transporting, and moving reindeer” (Table A3). In addition, negotiations and paperwork related to developments of other land uses on the pasture area belonged to women’s tasks. Based on

the assumption that women have better social skills than men, and that the other party behaves better towards women, female herders are often expected to act as negotiators. Various land-use conflicts constitute a significant burden to herding families: there are even threats and fear of violence, and deliberate harming of reindeer. Another topic that was vigorously debated was the growing predation pressure, which causes an economic burden and affects the well-being of the entire reindeer herding family (Rasmus et al., 2020). This situation has created new responsibilities for women: “protecting the herd from predators,” “searching for carcasses,” “participating in hunting predators,” and related paperwork (Table A3). It also influences the division of labor, as hunting requires time and rescheduling. In this situation, women considered themselves moral support and backing for their husbands and HD officials. Notably, women considered their role in maintaining the social well-being of their herding communities to be important. They did so by providing emotional support and maintaining relationships.

3.6. The agency of female herders in the male-dominated livelihood

The participants of all three workshops agreed that herding work in forests and fells is still largely perceived as ‘men’s work’. However, they had different views on the gender norms and roles associated with this livelihood. Participants had varying perceptions about whether women should be more actively involved in “men’s work” or if the traditional gender division would be desirable. Herding and gathering of reindeer continues to be done mostly by men, but nowadays women participate more in gatherings than earlier. Not all participants thought that participation of women in gathering work would be desirable, and the different roles of women and men were seen as a practical solution. One participant said she finds it hard to believe that women in her HD would ever participate in gathering, and concluded her comment with the question “and why should they?” Her view was that participation in gathering should not be taken as a sign of being a “real” reindeer herder. If everyone spent all their time in the forest, they would not be able to take care of all the other work.

According to participants, it is still a common assumption that it is the boys who will become a herder – but some participants felt strongly against this. Nevertheless, gender restricts choices made at an early age less than it did some decades ago. In the best case, there is space for each reindeer person to find a suitable role for themselves. Despite differing views on gender roles, it was agreed that a person’s suitability for a job is determined more by their personality and passion for the work than by their gender. One workshop participant mentioned that her “grandchild breaks the customary practices and shows others that a girl can do this as well”.

The number of young women working as herders, despite their spouses having different professions, is growing. One of the workshop participants mentioned that when she was 18 years old she was the only

girl working inside the round-up enclosure. Now during round-ups, there may be breaks for breastfeeding. Although workshop participants had experienced constraints on their agency, they also felt capable of acting. Women and girls have long had to “fight” for their status among male-dominated herding communities. Participants told that when they were younger, it was hard for them to directly present one’s own ideas to male herders – to get accepted, the ideas had to be presented indirectly. Female herders considered that due to having less physical strength, they often need to find ways to work smarter, not harder, and to innovate new ways. Women could rationalize reindeer herding and gathering: for example, less force is needed to get reindeer into the fence when dogs facilitate the workload. They can see many tasks from a different viewpoint, and can bring alternative experiences and practices from other HDs. Several participants mentioned that the acceptance and validation from male herders is still needed, however, and they shared their experiences of positive attention and (rare) praise that they had received for their participation in herding. Little by little, women have begun to receive recognition for their ideas and work, and also the older generation of herders have started to appreciate them.

3.7. The future hopes of female herders

During the workshops, the future role of women as reindeer owners, in the management, and in livelihood practices was discussed. Overall, the outlook was optimistic. Participants mentioned equality, communality, collaboration, continuity of “traditional” reindeer herding as a family-based activity, as well as modern techniques which have facilitated women’s participation in the herding. According to the participants, the gendered division of labor in reindeer herding should fade, so that everyone can participate as “an equal reindeer person”, according to their personal capabilities and motivation. They envisioned their future selves as multiskilled reindeer herders who possess the knowledge, skills and knowhow needed in reindeer husbandry. The participants’ belief in themselves and their agency at work was very high.

The participants also predicted that there will be more women in official roles in reindeer husbandry, and hoped that more women would enter the livelihood. Women are needed, because there is not enough workforce otherwise. It is good that also women can inherit reindeer and continue the livelihood. The participants were still concerned about the viability and continuity of reindeer herding as a livelihood. Decreasing number of herders was seen as a problem, as well as aging of herders, especially male herders without a spouse and a family.

There are young herders entering the livelihood, but due to the limits of the “largest allowed” reindeer quota in each HD, making a living in reindeer husbandry often remains uncertain. Participants considered it positive when people from outside the herding community enter the livelihood, or when a herder has been working elsewhere and comes back with fresh views. This has often been experienced within the communities of participants. The participants hoped that more children would participate in the herding work. They felt partly forced, but also very inspired, to combine traditional meat production with other businesses to get extra income. Combining new lines of other businesses, e.g. arts and handicraft has a potential to increase not only the profitability, but also the diversity of the livelihood. This was seen as a development that would create new opportunities for women.

The participants reported that rapidly increasing other land uses, predators and impacts of climate change are the most significant future threats to reindeer husbandry; these also greatly affect women’s role and work (Fig. 9). The participants hoped that land-use conflicts would cease and that outsiders would support, rather than persecute, reindeer herders. They also hoped that land-use and predator politics would favor herders more than they do now.

4. Discussion

4.1. Roles of women in reindeer husbandry

We employed the lenses of practice theory, agency, and the gendered use of space to better understand the contemporary roles of women in reindeer husbandry. We gave voice to the women of reindeer-herding families by examining their perceptions and experiences as described by themselves. The three workshops showed that reindeer husbandry is much more than actual herding. Tasks and practices of women – what women do – are as diverse as licensed hunting of predators and reindeer slaughter, caring for animals, traditional handicrafts, office work, conflict management, housekeeping, and work on family relations. Workshop participants view their work in reindeer husbandry as holistic, with care work and herding tasks intertwining. Along with earlier studies, such as Leonardo’s (1987) study on “work of kinship”, MacGregor et al. (2022) on care work, and Buchanan et al.’s (2016) research, our study broadens the perception of what constitutes work. It is clear that practices have been and still are guided by social conventions regarding what is considered appropriate for a herder of a certain gender. However, over the past few decades, there have been significant changes in practices and related perceptions of what constitutes, for example, women’s work in reindeer husbandry. Due to technical modernization and new tasks, such as preparations for land-use negotiations and communication through social media, new ways of doing things have emerged. The way in which male and female herders carry out their work is changing. It could be argued that some of them emphasise their personal traits and capabilities rather than their gender (Choi and Fuqua, 2003).

In any case, the constraints and inequalities that limit the agency of female herders are evident at all levels of their livelihoods, including institutional and organizational levels. Our study showed that the proportion of women both in the practice and management of reindeer husbandry in the 2020s is still low, although the share of females among reindeer owners as well as trustees and employees of HDs is increasing. Compared to a previous study, the share of female reindeer owners increased from 22 % in 1990/1991 (Jääskö, 1998) to 32 % in 2020/2021 (this study). During the same time period, the share of reindeer owned by women increased from 13 % (Jääskö, 1998) to 18 % in our study. Since 1995, a similar trend has been observed both in Sweden and in Finland. Of all reindeer owners in Sweden, 35–40 % are women, and they own 18–21 % of all reindeer (Asztalos Morell, 2021).

The increasing number of women owning more reindeer is important for decision-making in each HD because shareholders’ voting rights are determined by the number of reindeer they own. These observations seem to indicate a cultural trend among reindeer herding families: giving daughters their own earmark is becoming more common. The girls are now increasingly seen as likely continuers of the livelihood and tradition as the boys (Rehtonen, 2019). As it used to be common that girls had their earmarks and their own reindeer, at least in the Sámi herding tradition (Bäckman, 1985; Kylli, 2021), this development may also be seen as a return to “old practices”. It seems that in some HDs, women are taking on more significant and visible roles that may contribute importantly to their households’ economy. Our study showed signs that women have begun to play a larger role in herding communities’ public relations by working as treasurers and conflict mediators with local landowners.

4.2. Regional variation in women’s work

Our study revealed significant variations in the roles and responsibilities of women in reindeer husbandry in different RHA regions, perhaps mirroring varying capabilities to act, and differences in how women’s agency is promoted. The appointment of women to the HD board has been somewhat more common in the Sámi homeland than elsewhere. In southern RHA, where reindeer husbandry is more often a secondary occupation and most herders are Finnish, several HDs had no

record of women serving on the board or as staff from 1984/1985 to 2021/2022. This is most likely due to the small scale of stationary reindeer husbandry in southern RHA, where labor division was traditionally gendered: men took care of the herds while women took care of the children and cattle at home (Kortessalmi, 2007).

Discussions in the Rovaniemi and Kuusamo workshops revealed that women's tasks focused more on conflicts with other land users than those in the northern Inari workshop. This is because there is more rapidly increasing land use south of the Sámi homeland due to less strict legal protection compared to the rest of the RHA (Koivurova et al., 2015). In the Kuusamo region, women have many predator-related tasks because abundant predator populations cross the Russian border and cause serious reindeer losses in Finland (Rasmus et al., 2020). Regional differences in women's work in reindeer husbandry were also evident in Jääskö's (1998) study, which lacked participation from southern HDs. The study showed that, in the Sámi homeland, women participated more in herding work and HD tasks, which require the ability to identify reindeer owners' earmarks. In the northeastern RHA, however, women spent more time on other aspects of reindeer husbandry, such as business activities, training reindeer dogs, and attending courses (Jääskö, 1998).

4.3. Factors limiting and promoting women's agency

Women in reindeer husbandry consider themselves as individuals with agency – willing to and capable of acting based on their identity and also based on their cultural patterns. Considering the main elements of agency and how women experience them – voluntariness, structures and resources enabling choices, and the power to choose one's own course of action – certain factors were especially seen to shape the structures and resources enabling choices (Eteläpelto et al., 2013; Manlosa, 2022). For example, the ability of female herders, especially mothers of young children, to participate in certain activities was limited or promoted by their social networks, the suitability of the municipal daycare system, and the attitude of the local school.

Interesting discussions were held regarding the factors that promote or constrain agency of female herders (Hobson, 2011; Hobson et al., 2013). Our workshop participants found that technical modernization, including new vehicles and tools, supports a more equal division of work. These findings contrast with those of Amft (2000) and Buchanan et al. (2016). They suggested that mechanization leads to the masculinization of herding and the marginalization of others from core tasks, for example, by avoidance of the use of snowmobiles or ATVs. Conversely, Uden (2010) found that female herders are open to new digital tools and are key players in the ongoing digitalization of reindeer husbandry. Many participants seemed enthusiastic about educating themselves, and they were highly educated. Although pursuing higher education means spending less time on herding work, through which traditional knowledge is passed on and practical skills are learned (Porsanger and Guttorm, 2011; Magga, 2024), women can contribute other valuable skills to their HDs. It has been common for women to seek education and employment outside the home, while men have continued the physical work of herding. This aligns with the broader trend in Finland, where women overall have higher education levels than men, with the largest differences observed in rural and remote areas (MAF, 2017). According to Buchanan et al. (2016), men may be more vulnerable than women to the effects of fluctuating economic and climatic risks and less qualified to transition to other forms of employment. Women are more likely to have a higher level of personal resilience.

The elements of agency have varied throughout history. In discussions about their mothers' and grandmothers' roles in reindeer husbandry, the participants' perspectives were in line with Jääskö's (1998) study, which showed that the general attitude in the 1990s was that women played no significant role in the livelihood. The expectations and assumptions about genders change alongside societal changes;

climatological and ecological changes within the RHA also have an impact. Recent challenges, such as decreasing profitability of the livelihood, high predation losses and increasing need for winter feeding, were central themes discussed in our workshops. Diversifying the livelihood is considered as a way to adapt to changing environments and to strengthen resilience (Turunen et al., 2016). Nowadays, this is often achieved through women's participation in reindeer tourism operations or employment outside home (Ruotsala, 2007).

Almost all of the workshop participants anticipated that women would play a strong role in the future. Joona and Keskitalo (2021) and Paldanius (2021) have also made this finding. Desired future visions included elements such as communality, working together as a family, the continuation of traditional herding with the help of modern technology, and a stronger role for female herders in the governance of their livelihood.

4.4. The gendered use of space in reindeer husbandry

As a livelihood, reindeer husbandry uses land extensively, and herding tasks are carried out in different places (Helle and Jaakkola, 2008). Some activities occur at home or nearby, while others are linked to the mobility of reindeer, seasonal pasture rotation, and gathering animals over long distances. In this sense, the concept of place and social relations in space, are very different for reindeer herders (independent on gender) than for practitioners of more sedentary rural livelihoods (Rasmus et al., 2021). The gendered use of space has been studied for example in feminist geography with the assumption that women are more likely than men to experience spatial behaviour restricted to the home or close to home (see Massey, 1984, 1994; McDowell, 1993a, 1993b; Sireni, 2002).

Our workshop discussions revealed that the idea of private spaces as 'feminine' and public spaces as 'masculine' (McDowell, 1993a; Sireni, 2002) seems to still hold partly true in contemporary reindeer husbandry in Finland. Participants told that women typically have the main responsibility for the household tasks, which mostly take place at home and in the yard and require regular presence at home, whereas men take care of the tasks that require spending more time in the yard and further away from home (Fig. 7). These experiences are in line with previous studies (Jääskö, 1998; Ruotsala, 2007, 2009). Jääskö (1998) observed nearly three decades ago that by working and taking a year-round mental responsibility for housekeeping, women enable male herders to spend time away from home with the reindeer. In the 1990s, as many as 90 % of the work done by women in reindeer husbandry was counted as "invisible work" (Jääskö, 1998). On the other hand, our study showed that the concept of gendered spaces is becoming blurred in reindeer husbandry. Due to safer and more useable vehicles, women can now work far from home, while men stay home with the children. Also, the home is not the only place where care is provided in reindeer husbandry. Even small children may accompany their parents to summer calf marking, for example.

4.5. Limits and potential of our work

The experiences and views of female and young herders are less frequently heard than those of established male herders. We acknowledge that a binary categorization does not reflect the actual diversity of sex and gender present in reindeer herding communities. We also acknowledge that gender roles are socially constructed and recognize the importance of hearing from individuals of various sex categorizations and gender identities. We recognize that the workshop discussions reported in this study may seem to perpetuate gender stereotypes at first glance. But to begin to understand the changing gender roles in different herding communities, we find it useful and empowering to discuss the roles, behaviors, and identities of self-identified women in these communities. It is also important to note that there are many views on gender equality; different gender roles can be seen as complementary

and equally valuable. These different views were heard during our workshop discussions.

In a rural context, the subordinate position of women is often assumed (Sireni, 2002). Nevertheless, according to their own perceptions, women on Finnish smallholdings have been described as having a strong position. Women have long participated in decision-making processes, received at least half of the farm income, and farmer men have defined their wives' profession as that of a farmer (Sireni, 2002). Rural women also have higher levels of education than rural men (Högbacka and Siiskonen, 1996). In our work, we did not make assumptions about inequalities or gender-based power imbalances. Although we identified a strong sense of capability and agency, we also heard about inequalities and constraints that undermine certain aspects of this. We heard experiences about "fighting to be heard" and the struggle to be accepted as a female herder.

There are still institutional and organizational constraints on livelihoods (Hobson, 2011). Figs. 2–4 illustrate the issue of reindeer ownership, while Fig. 5 shows the issue of the roles of women in the management of the livelihood. There is basically no research on equality issues and discrimination within reindeer husbandry in Finland, and our work does not shed much new light on these topics. Studies on these topics have been carried out in Norway (Joks, 2001, 2007; Eikjok, 2007; Kuokkanen, 2007). Legislation related to structural subsidies ("Laki porotalouden ja luontaiselinkeinojen rakennetuista" 26.8.2011/986) and to substitute services ("Laki poronhoitajien sijaisavusta" 19.12.2014/1238) have been mentioned as examples of discriminatory structures in reindeer husbandry in Finland. Women are often in practice left without subsidies: only one person from one family can get start-up support, and pregnancy, giving birth and caring for a sick child are not reasons to get substitute services, according to present-day legislation (Magga, 2024). State governance and its legislation that entered northern Fennoscandia has historically affected the equality of property ownership and inheritance in Sámi herding communities (Kuokkanen, 2009). These structural inequalities, descriptions of colonial histories, and darker personal experiences (Lehvonon, 2023) like harassment and even abuse did not come up in our workshops. Reason for this is most probably the short format and "light-hearted" and consensus-seeking atmosphere (Chambers et al., 2022). Still, the experiences of workshop participants mirror those of young female herders in Sweden (Kaiser et al., 2015): while the lifestyle is joyful and invigorating, it is also harsh and conflictual.

Participatory workshops like ours have their restrictions, but still – particularly when combined with archival data and statistics – they bring forward holistic information. While participatory observation as a method provides first-hand evidence of what people do, and interviews offer access to inner thoughts and the reasons for actions, participatory workshops have a potential to combine both (Ørngreen and Levinsen, 2017). The workshop as a method enabled participation of a large group of female herders in a constructive and enthusiastic atmosphere (Chambers et al., 2022). The workshops proved to provide a useful research outcome. Participants expressed the view that the workshop also provided them with a welcomed opportunity to share their experiences with other women from reindeer-herding families – networking was considered useful and inspiring. Our research process aimed at co-production of knowledge; bringing knowledge of practitioners

together with other types of research material (Doering et al., 2022). Research processes such as this, action research, can also function as catalysts for social learning and empowerment.

To conclude, our work has increased the knowledge related to the role of women in reindeer husbandry in Finland. As Silvasti (2003) observed in her studies on gendered labor divisions on farms, the role of women in rural areas is becoming more diverse. The role and agency of women in reindeer husbandry have varied throughout history and are now transforming again. Our study shows that from various discourses describing the role of women within agriculture in Europe (Brandth, 2002; Shortall, 2006), the contemporary role of women in reindeer husbandry has clearly begun to change towards the discourse of diversity, in which women with strong agency actively construct their roles.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Minna Turunen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sirpa Rasmus:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Teresa Komu:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Iida Melamies:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Tuulia Väärälä:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Vesa-Pekka Inget:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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APPENDICES.

Text A1. Description of the archival research

In the archival research we focused on studying the gender division of the boards of approximately 54 HDs⁴ by examining their annual

⁴ There have been changes to the number and formation of cooperatives through our study period.

management reports. The reports are available at the archives of the Provincial Museum in Oulu (-1982) and the Reindeer Herders' Association in Rovaniemi (1982–2022). Individual HDs may keep their own, more detailed archival records but these are not publicly available. We looked through all the material that was in Oulu, which consisted of very few reports from the period 1927–1941, some from the period 1943–1948, and then of more consistent records from the period 1949/1950–1981/1982. From 1948 and onwards, the HDs have been obliged to compile an annual management report to the Reindeer Herders' Association,⁵ and the reporting has covered the whole RHA. Before that, the records are very fragmentary, except for the year 1939/1940. For example, annual management reports between the years 1942–1945 are largely absent due to the turmoil of the Second World War. Our analytical focus is therefore on the period from 1949/1950 to 2020/2021. It is perhaps worthwhile to mention in any case that there are no women to be found in any official role in the older records, which, of course, still does not mean that there were not any.

We calculated the proportion of women and men within the boards and the staff annually for 1949/1950–1981/1982, due to only three different statuses that were kept record of and the very small number of women overall in the records. For the period 1982–2022, only every fifth report was investigated. Most of the annual management reports from the period between 1949/1950 and 1981/1982 only include the names of the Chief of District, the Vice-chief of District and the treasurer, but not all of them are always mentioned. Sometimes the Chief of District and the treasurer are the same person and at times a secretary is mentioned. From 1976/1977 onwards, the names of board members of the cooperatives start to appear in the annual management reports, also in the form of handwritten signatures. Before that, mentions of them are scattered. From 1984 onwards, the documentation of board members can be considered to be reliable, because all names of the members are listed as well as other staff, such as countmen, and the minutes are typed.

In the material from the period between 1949/1950 and 1981/1982, the reports are mostly handwritten. This means that the gender of the person of each status can mainly be found out only by interpreting whether the first name in their hand-written signatures is a male or a female one. This requires knowledge of the gendered nature of both Finnish and Sámi first names and of the style of old handwriting. During the 1960s and onwards, typewritten reports are becoming more common, though the names continue to be mostly handwritten signatures. In unclear cases, comparing several reports with the same signature often made interpreting the signature possible or, in some cases, the name had been typewritten somewhere in a report. However, the signatures were not always legible, and those cases were indicated in our statistics as “unclear”. Only in cases where the researcher felt certain of the name belonging to a female were marked as “woman”. No names of the persons were written down during the analysis phase and only a record of the gender of each status was tracked.

All this understandably causes some degree of unreliability to the results of the older material and its analytical power is very limited regarding the official roles of women in reindeer husbandry. It is also possible that some women are missing, or some men have been incorrectly interpreted as women. However, we do believe that it is possible to trace quite reliably the development of the gender division in two statuses over seven decades: the Chief of District and the treasurer. The reports from the period 1981/1982–2020/2021 on the other hand, enable a more thorough analysis of the different official roles held by women within the cooperatives, how they have changed through four decades and of the geographical differences in them.

Table A1

Number of reindeer owners divided into gender and age classes within the RHA (Reindeer Herders' Association, 2024).

Reindeer herding year	Gender	Age class							Total number	Share of gender (%)
		0–17	18–24	25–34	35–44	45–54	55–64	65–		
1990/1991	male	162	270	742	1013	1041	1225	1581	6034	80
1990/1991	female	43	79	163	230	279	246	489	1529	20
1995/1996	male	75	211	560	697	935	1066	1742	5286	77
1995/1996	female	39	111	198	201	283	283	484	1599	23
2000/2001	male	491	324	477	792	934	598	597	4213	75
2000/2001	female	267	123	164	251	266	185	164	1420	25
2005/2006	male	410	273	389	594	760	672	570	3668	74
2005/2006	female	268	101	155	218	230	183	166	1321	26
2010/2011	male	323	251	377	399	633	730	540	3253	72
2010/2011	female	243	126	169	177	238	201	142	1296	28
2015/2016	male	323	226	361	384	531	611	645	3081	70
2015/2016	female	245	114	169	181	214	197	175	1295	30
2020/2021	male	301	172	343	408	373	532	766	2895	68
2020/2021	female	247	111	193	200	187	220	199	1357	32
2021/2022	male	335	175	352	409	369	530	720	2890	68
2021/2022	female	257	117	197	202	192	220	188	1373	32

Table A2

The reindeer ownership structure has changed

Year	Number of eligible reindeer	Number of applicants
1995	25	2031
1996	25	2002
1997	25	2047
1998	35	1542
1999	50	1328
2000	50	1331
2001	60	1116

(continued on next page)

⁵ In 1948 Reindeer Herders' Association is established and it replaces the previous Poronjalostusyhdistys also as a record keeper.

Table A2 (continued)

Year	Number of eligible reindeer	Number of applicants
2002	70	1062
2003	70	1028
2004	80	1026

Table A3

Summary of the current seasonal tasks reported by the female reindeer herders participating in the workshops in Rovaniemi, Kuusamo and Inari.

WOMEN'S WORK IN REINDEER HUSBANDRY ROUND THE YEAR		
- Housekeeping: care of family members: dietary and clothing maintenance; care of gear; office work; cleaning; driving		
SUMMER		
Rovaniemi	Kuusamo	Inari
To produce and make preparations for winter feeds To repair and build fences 'Calf marking Office work (e.g. VAT) - To take "harmful" reindeer away from agricultural fields etc. To search for carcasses To check and take care of reindeer (e.g. antler damage) To train reindeer dogs To participate in annual meeting of RHA To gather materials for handicraft	To produce and make preparations for winter feeds To repair and build fences Calf marking Office work (e.g. VAT, application for agricultural support) To take "harmful reindeer" away from agricultural fields etc. To search for carcasses To check and take care of reindeer (e.g. orphan calves) To participate in annual meeting of RHA	To produce and make preparations for winter feeds To repair and build fences Calf marking Office work (e.g. ALV, project work) To participate in annual meeting of RHA To make preparations for reindeer-based tourism services (e.g. to coat sleighs with tar, marketing)
AUTUMN		
Rovaniemi	Kuusamo	Inari
To acquire lichens for winter To repair and build fences To gather reindeer Round-up (e.g. to draw animals, to take notes, to load animals into trucks) To equip reindeer with satellite collars Work related to slaughter Meat processing (e.g. to cut, to pack, to transport) Office work (e.g. to organize autumn meeting, to make financial statement, fiscal declaration, applications for substitutes and compensations, to order supplies, to sell and to market meat and other products) To search for carcasses To train reindeer (for tourism and racing) and dogs Reindeer-based tourism activities (e.g. reindeer taxi) Handicraft	To acquire lichens for winter To feed reindeer To repair and build fences To gather reindeer Round-up Work related to slaughter Meat processing (to take internal organs, to cut, to sell, to transport) To equip reindeer with satellite collars To soften hides Office work (e.g. to organize autumn meeting, to provide ADP support, bookkeeping, to market) To search for carcasses, To be a driver	To acquire lichens and other forage (e.g. hay, pellets) for winter To gather reindeer Roundups (e.g. to load animals into the trucks, to transport animals) To stop the traffic To equip reindeer with collars Work related to slaughter To process meat (e.g. to cut, to pack, to market, to sell, to transport) To clean and nail hides Office work (e.g. to organize autumn meeting, financial planning, financial statement, book keeping, to order labels, contacts with clients)
WINTER		
Rovaniemi	Kuusamo	Inari
To feed reindeer To take care of fences, to take reindeer into enclosures To gather reindeer Round up Work related to slaughter Meat processing (e.g. to sell) To search, transport and move reindeer To take "harmful reindeer" to right places To take care of reindeer, vaccinations, medication To search for carcasses To train reindeer for racing and tourism To participate in racing competitions Reindeer-based tourism activities (sledge reindeer, visits to reindeer	To feed reindeer To take care of enclosures To gather reindeer, and transport them home To catch reindeer in a poor condition Office work (e.g. bookkeeping of agriculture) To search for carcasses, to protect herd from predators, to shoot predators To train reindeer and reindeer dogs To participate in reindeer racing competitions Reindeer-based tourism activities	To feed reindeer To gather reindeer Round-ups Work related to slaughter Meat processing To prepare hides To take care of reindeer To train reindeer Reindeer-based tourism activities Handicraft (e.g. to prepare reindeer leg leather)

(continued on next page)

Table A3 (continued)

WOMEN'S WORK IN REINDEER HUSBANDRY ROUND THE YEAR		
- Housekeeping: care of family members: dietary and clothing maintenance; care of gear; office work; cleaning; driving		
SUMMER		
Rovaniemi	Kuusamo	Inari
farm, reindeer taxi) Handicraft	To assist with traffic accidents involving reindeer	
SPRING		
Rovaniemi	Kuusamo	Inari
To feed reindeer To repair fences To take care of calving To ear-mark calves, and 1-yr-old male calves not marked earlier To take reindeer into summer pastures To prepare dried meat To equip reindeer with satellite collars Office work (e.g. spring meeting, VAT, to take reindeer statistics, POMU) To search for carcasses, to estimate damage due to accidents To train reindeer dogs and reindeer (e.g. sledge reindeer) To castrate, to tame reindeer, To mark touristic and racing reindeer	To feed reindeer To prepare agricultural fields To repair and build fences To take reindeer into right herding districts To take care of calving To equip reindeer with satellite collars To take reindeer into summer pastures To search, transport and move reindeer To take "harmful reindeer" into right places Office work (e.g. spring meeting, VAT, book-keeping of agriculture) Office work (e.g. spring meeting, VAT, book-keeping) To search for carcasses, To castrate Handicraft To be a driver To assist with traffic accidents of reindeer	To feed reindeer, to herd reindeer from one pasture area to another To repair and build fences (e.g. to cut poles) Work related to slaughter- To prepare dry meat To monitor reindeer in the forest and by applications To take care of calving To equip reindeer with satellite collars To mark reindeer not marked earlier To move herds from one place to another Office work (e.g. VAT, to organize meetings, to participate in trainings) To train reindeer for tourism. To castrate reindeer To participate in reindeer races Reindeer-based tourism services Handicraft (e.g. to prepare sisnas, dry hides) To gather antlers

The structure of reindeer ownership has changed significantly in recent decades. Finland's EU membership in 1995 represented a turning point in the transformation of agricultural policy and support systems (Lindén et al., 2008). Consequently, reindeer husbandry can be viewed as part of a broader social and political transformation, particularly given the argument that policies and support measures implemented by the Finnish Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry changed as a result of EU membership (Lindén et al., 2008).

The state's support policy has driven a change in reindeer ownership, resulting in larger herds becoming concentrated among fewer owners. Consequently, the number of individuals involved in reindeer husbandry has inevitably declined. The introduction of national, animal-based support schemes (Ruokavirasto, 2025) has greatly influenced the age distribution of reindeer owners. As shown in the table below, the number of eligible reindeer increased from 25 in 1995 to 50 in 2000. During this period, the number of applicants for support also decreased (ELY Centre, 2025). This is to be expected, as those with fewer reindeer naturally fall outside the scope of support unless they purchase additional reindeer. In this context, it is possible that older people sold their reindeer to younger people. This could explain the decrease in the older age group among reindeer owners and the corresponding increase in the younger age group. At the same time, the maximum permitted number of reindeer for the entire RHA fell from 220,900 to 203,700 (Reindeer Herders' Association, 2025).

Data availability

Part of the data will be made available on request

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